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Electricity Consumption Forecasting and Digital Energy Management in the White Goods Manufacturing Sector

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ABSTRACT

Electricity is the most widely used type of energy in the production sector. It has a direct impact on the cost of electrical energy and sustainability in production processes. In order to ensure electricity supply security, accurate forecasting methods must be applied. With the integration of digitalization into the production sector, data collected from production is analyzed and more effective decision-making processes are supported. In this study, estimation models were developed based on the electricity consumption of machines used in the oven business of a white goods manufacturing company. By taking the electrical energy data consumed by a machine in a certain time interval, different estimation methods were applied and energy consumption for the next period was estimated. In this way, cost calculations were made and energy management processes were improved. Digitalization in the manufacturing sector increases efficiency while also reducing costs. Analyzing data collected from machines on digital platforms helps businesses manage and optimize their production processes more effectively. Planning energy use with accurate estimates provides businesses with both sustainability and cost advantages. Digitalization also offers opportunities such as monitoring machine performance, detecting faults in advance, and developing planned maintenance strategies. As a result, digitalization plays a critical role in sustainability and competitive advantage by ensuring effective management of electrical energy in the manufacturing sector. In this study, since electrical energy is a scarce and valuable resource, alternative forecasting models with high modeling success were analyzed to support planned consumption and strategic decision processes.

1 INTRODUCTION

Electrical energy is an indispensable element of our lives. The same applies to the production sector [1]. Electricity is very important for continuous, high-quality and safe production in the production sector. In the manufacturing sector, as production increases, electricity consumption increases in direct proportion. The electrical energy consumed by the machines used in the business is sometimes unusual [2]. This situation causes an inevitable increase in costs for the business, and poor quality and inefficient production. The increasing competition every passing day has made it a

necessity for businesses to use all kinds of resources in the most efficient way. This necessity has caused productivity measurements, precautions to be taken and steps to be taken more seriously in businesses. On the other hand, with the effect of continuously developing technology, significant changes have occurred in production environments, both in production technologies and quality control activities, as well as in organizational and operational activities within the enterprise. Measuring and monitoring productivity has also become mandatory for enterprises that want to catch up with the change in every field where these changes are experienced [3].

The white goods industry has a special and important place in the Turkish manufacturing sector with its technology, product designs, increasing production and export capacity. In addition, the sub-industry, which grows parallel to the development of the main white goods industry, provides remarkable contributions to the Turkish economy with its dealer and service network, employment and export opportunities. The Turkish white goods sector has a wide range of products from the large household appliances sector to the small household appliances sector [4].

Electricity consumption is one of the most important development indicators of a country. The increasing need for electricity every year in our rapidly developing country can be met by establishing new power plants with a variety of resources and increasing the efficient use of electricity [5].

The purpose of this research is to keep the limited and expensive source of electricity under control and estimating the electric energy consumption for the future years by using previous consumption data to take action for the future. In light of the action, the cost calculation in a white goods manufacturing company is to calculate the electricity consumption per product. An alarm application was developed to prevent waste and damage to machines used in production during the monitoring of electricity consumption. Both medium- and long-term demand forecasts are very important for the strategic planning of the electricity grid and the scheduling of maintenance activities, the establishment of new generation and transmission capacities, and activities aimed at developing the grid, such as long-term demand side management [6, 7].

This study emphasizes that digitalization is increasing in the white goods sector. Recording and analyzing electricity consumption data can be done more effectively with the technological opportunities offered by digitalization. In addition, alarm systems used during electricity consumption allow for timely detection of errors and taking strategic steps to increase energy efficiency as a result of digitalization. These systems help businesses improve their electricity consumption management while also optimizing costs and achieving sustainability goals.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

In general, all of these studies show that methods such as artificial neural networks [10,11,12], regression analysis [10,15,16,17,18,19,20], genetic algorithms [21] and structural time series [22] have achieved significant success in electrical energy demand forecasting.

In this study, ARIMA, Regression Analysis and DeepAR methods were used to control operating costs, ensure production continuity and increase competitiveness in the white goods sector. As a result of the literature review, it was observed that the most commonly used methods in data sets containing time data were ARIMA and Linear Regression. For this reason, ARIMA and Linear Regression methods were preferred.

DeepAR, on the other hand, was developed by Amazon and stands out with its ability to handle trends, seasonality, variable scales and dynamic structures in time series. This method will be used due to its superior performance compared to other models in predictions made on large data sets and complex structures.

3 APPLICATION

The workflow is mentioned in Figure 1. The literature review was conducted and the prediction models used in other studies were investigated. This research aims to increase the accuracy and reliability of electricity consumption estimations, which are of critical importance for businesses.

Figure 1: Work Flow of the study

In particular, estimations made using models such as ARIMA, Linear Regression and DeepAR allow businesses to plan and manage electricity consumption more effectively. This accuracy can increase the reliability of the developed alarm system, allowing it to detect abnormal electricity consumption data from the machine more precisely and intervene correctly. Thus, businesses can minimize machine errors by taking timely precautions, increase energy savings and ensure production continuity by reducing unplanned stops. This process can increase the operational efficiency and competitive advantage of businesses by emphasizing the strong integration of digitalization and data-driven approaches. As a result, this estimation and alarm system approach can contribute to increasing the success of businesses by providing a more robust and reliable production environment.

Table 2. One Week Energy Consumption Data from the Machine

Tarih-Saat:	TR1-SY01->TR1 MasterPack ->Aktif Enerji	TR1-SY01->TR1 MasterPack ->Endüktif ReAktif Enerji	TR1-SY01->TR1 MasterPack ->Kapasitif ReAktif Enerji
20.03.2023 00:01	2.673,8	N/A	4.718,6
21.03.2023 00:01	2.832,2	N/A	4.939,9
22.03.2023 00:01	2.961,9	N/A	4.968,3
23.03.2023 00:01	2.721,0	N/A	5.079,4
24.03.2023 00:01	2.865,1	N/A	4.672,1
25.03.2023 00:01	2.804,9	N/A	4.444,7
26.03.2023 00:01	N/A	N/A	266,4
*			

Electricity consumption was estimated using ARIMA, Linear Regression and DeepAr methods on electricity consumption data taken from machines. Electricity consumptions for 2019, 2020 and 2021 were taken from a machine in a bakery business.

The reason for considering the years 2019, 2020, 2021 is that the number of machines working in these 3 years is close to the number of machines working today. Therefore, in order to obtain more accurate results, the data of the last 3 years was taken as basis.

For the electricity consumption data of the Furnace department for 2019, 2020 and 2021, the ARIMA, Linear Regression and DeepAr methods, which are the most suitable for the data set and the result of the literature review, were used.

3.1 Forecasting

Table 2 shows the comparison of RMSE values in the Method and Platform. Due to the small amount of data in the dataset, the DeepAR method did not work efficiently and the RMSE values were higher than the other methods.

Table 2. RMSE Platform and Method Comparison

<i>Method / Platform</i>	<i>Python</i>	<i>R</i>
<i>ARIMA</i>	1062.288	1085.27
<i>Linear Regression</i>	1463.5746	1275.765
<i>DeepAR</i>	7662.58	NA

3.2 Alarm System Application

The business unit enters the machine it wants to control and the reference values of the machine into the web application. In the reference values, the minimum value is entered to control the maximum consumption level of the machine and the machine's non-operation status on Sunday and A shifts.

Figure 12: Developed Application Flow Diagram

Windows is triggered once an hour. It collects the electricity consumption of the machine 1 hour ago and if there is an unrelated situation regarding the machine, it sends an e-mail to the relevant work unit.

If the maximum electricity consumption of the machine is exceeded, the relevant work unit controls the machine. The machine's extra motor may have been left on. There may be a malfunction in the machine. If the machine is left on Sundays and during the A shift when it should not work, unnecessary energy consumption is prevented. It eliminates the operator's manual control and the situation of being overlooked. Since the machine's consumption data is determined in advance, it reduces the machine failure rate. In addition, when applying data mining on electricity consumption data, non-reference (lower-upper) values were removed from the data set with pre-processing. Since the developed alarm system will reduce non-reference data, less non-reference data will be detected in pre-processing. Thus, it is anticipated that more reliable results will be obtained (Figure 12).

Thanks to the developed application, it has been reduced from 246,675 TL to 218,854 TL. Thus, a profit of 27,821.85 TL has been achieved. This approach makes the factory's energy management more efficient and reduces energy costs in the long term. It also supports the factory's social and environmental responsibility by increasing environmental sustainability. As a result, the application is developed and its database-based approach are seen as an important step to increase the factory's energy efficiency and reduce costs. This type of innovation helps industrial companies achieve their sustainability goals.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, ARIMA, Linear Regression and DeepAR models were used to make predictions for the following years on electricity consumption data.

The ARIMA method worked most efficiently on the current data set on the Python platform. The data set should be taken in the long term and the DeepAR method should be run again in the next stage to measure its efficiency. Thus, the electricity consumption cost estimate for the next year can be made for the oven business that produces white goods.

With the warning system application to be developed later, the relevant unit will be warned in case of abnormal electricity consumption data coming from the machine. With the warning system, the fault occurring in the machine can be determined and fixed. While creating the data set, it was noticed that the electricity consumption values received from the machines were not in a standard structure. An alarm system application was developed to be able to instantly catch the out-of-reference values that occurred. In addition, out-of-reference values detected from the machine revealed that more motors were running than necessary for production, indicating a machine error. To address this issue, an alarm system was developed. This application contributes to energy savings and sends immediate alerts to the relevant work unit when a machine error occurs. As a result, unplanned downtime is prevented through predictive maintenance and early fault detection.

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